

GENDEROLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF MIMIC NONVERBAL MEANS

Akhmedov Botirjon Ravshanovich

Andijan State Institute of foreign languages, doctor of philosophy in
philological Sciences (PhD)

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Annotation: Facial expressions are made up of meaningful movements of a person's face. Mimics, like allusions, will be intended for an addressee, in other cases also used to provide certain information. Facial changes are applied for the purpose of complementing, replacing and following the thought being expressed.

Keywords: communication, verbal, nonverbal, contemplation, positive assessment, speech situation, pronunciation, pause, tone, social attitude.

One of the easiest ways to show kinetic movements is facial expressions. Obviously, judging by the words of people, depending on their faces, it is possible to determine their true psychological emotional state – their nervousness, surprise, anger or joy at something. The face and the many gestures and movements associated with it are not only associated with specific emotions, but also perform certain communicative and social tasks. Even the slightest changes in the face of the interlocutor in communication are very informative, and on their basis, people often make different decisions about the communication partner.

Although the expression of emotions often depends on culture, the rules of manifestation, individual differences and circumstances, there are a number of cultural expressions of emotions on the face. Facial expressions are biological innate motor actions and therefore serve as reliable diagnostic indicators of specific emotions.

Paul Ekman and Sylvain Tomkins have proven through their universe research that facial expressions of human emotions are universal. This claim was first put forward by Charles Darwin some 130 years ago in his book "the expression of emotions in Man and animals". At least eight of the facial expressions have been well researched, with Paul Ekman contributing. Having spent 50 years of his life studying the physiology of human emotions and facial expressions, he began this by studying facial expressions of a tribe living on a remote mountain in Papua

New Guinea, and was completely convinced of the universality of facial expressions¹.

The facial expressions of the well-studied eight senses are joy (satisfaction), anger (anger), sadness (frustration), fear (anxiety), admiration (surprise), disgust, disdain (arrogance) and shame (or feeling guilty).

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Since the main purpose of a person in the process of treatment is thought Exchange, in order to achieve this goal, a person, being a whole biological organism, tries to convey his opinion to the addressee through various ways and methods. As a result, facial nonverbal tools along with verbal tools are also used in speech communication.

Mimic nonverbal tools are among the most commonly used methods in expression of thought. Because on the face of a person, meaningful changes are expressed in communication-intervention, monological speech, internal monologue, thinking and silent State. 60% of the nonverbal tools used in ten minutes of dialogue during the observation of the process of circulation corresponded to mimic nonverbal tools, and even when various body, body movements, phonation nonverbal tools were used, mimic nonverbal tools were used as auxiliary tools, since since a person is a living being, in any information his reaction is manifested through facial organs².

Mimic nonverbal means represent emotional-psychological, symbolic, pictorial and indicative suggestive meanings. The face is an important descriptor of human physical appearance. The contraction of the facial muscles changes the expression in it and informs about the state of a person. They mean different meanings as a result of changes in the muscles of the lips, eyes, eyebrows, tongue, teeth, nose and face .

One of the indispensable aspects of the life of any person is speech communication, the most basic manifestation of information exchange of communication-intervention. When communication is carried out using nonverbal tools that complement the speech Message in the communication process of different individuals, a lot of differences can be observed. In particular, this condition is also observed among people of different sexes. Men and women differ significantly not only in terms of physical and physiological

¹ Бу ҳақда қаранг: Пиз А. Язык телодвижений // <https://booksonline.com.ua/view.php?book=168970>

² Саидхонов М. Алоқа-аралашув ва имо-ишоралар. – Тошкент: Фан, 2008. – Б. 67.

characteristics, but also in terms of psychological characteristics, personal characteristics, behavioral and communication characteristics. Therefore, in colloquial communication, they have their own mimic actions, which are important to analyze in the genderological aspect.

References:

- 1.Искандарова Ш. Ўзбек нутқ одатининг мулоқот шакллари: Филол. фан. номз. ...дисс. – Самарканд, 1993. – Б.105.
- 2.Выготский Л.С., Лурия А.Р. Этюды по истории поведения. – Москва, 1993. – С.93-95.
- 3.Тоирова Г. Ўзбек нутқий мулоқотида системавийлик ва информативлик: Филология фанлари бўйича фалсафа доктори (PhD) дисс. – Тошкент, 2017. – Б.42.
- 4.Нурмонов.А. Танланган асарлар III жилдлик .Iжилд . Т.2012.- С.213.
- 5.Юшман Н.В. Экстранормальная фонетика. 1930-х гг. [49,165 с.]
- 6.Нурмонов.А. Танланган асарлар III жилдлик .IIжилд . Т.2012.- С.40.
- 7.Верещагин Е.М. О своеобразии отражения мимики и жестов вербальными средствами. Вопросы языкознания [Текст] / Е. М. Верещагин, В. Г. Костомаров. – М.: Наука № 1, 1981. – С. 36 – 47
- 8.Горелов В. И. Стилистика китайского языка [Текст]/ В. И. Горелов. -М.: Изд-во военного института, 1974 - 132 с.
- 9.Экман, П. Узнай лжеца по выражению лица. – Спб.: Питер, 2010.-С.39